

SYNTHESIS OF VITAMIN D AND FACTORS INFLUENCING IT: GENETIC, ENVIRONMENTAL, AND INDIVIDUAL ASPECTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13866538>

Abstract. *This article investigates the factors influencing the synthesis of the vitamin D in the human body, genetic polymorphisms, and their impact on health. The obtained results indicate changes in vitamin D levels across various groups (elite athletes, patients with reproductive system diseases, individuals diagnosed with osteoporosis, and conditionally healthy individuals) based on genetic characteristics and other factors. Genetic analyses provided significant findings on the impact of VDR gene polymorphisms (FokI and BsmI) on human health. These results may serve as a basis for future research on early disease detection and the implementation of preventive measures.*

Keywords: *vitamin D Synthesis, Genetic Polymorphism, VDR Gene, Personalized Medicine, Disease Prevention.*

Introduction

The primary function of vitamin D, which is crucial for maintaining human health, is to regulate the absorption of calcium and phosphorus and contribute to the health of bones [6]. Additionally, research by leading contemporary scientists has shown that vitamin D also affects the immune system, muscle function, and even cognitive processes [7, 9]. Recent studies indicate that vitamin D plays a significant role in protecting against various diseases, including cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, osteoporosis, and cancer [3, 4, 10, 11].

In the practice of personalized medicine, assessing vitamin D synthesis on an individual level and developing appropriate and accurate treatment and prevention plans for each patient is essential [11]. This approach takes into account an individual's genetic profile, lifestyle, health status, and other factors, which helps improve overall health. Factors affecting vitamin D synthesis include the amount and quality of sunlight exposure, skin pigmentation, body weight and fat content, diet, physical activity, season and climate, clothing, skin care, health status, genetics, and other variables [12]. The presence of these factors is likely related to the level of an individual's living conditions and most factors are dependent on natural living conditions, which can significantly affect the level of vitamin D synthesis in the body. These factors may contribute to a decrease in vitamin D synthesis. Therefore, it is important to consider both individual and population-specific characteristics to maintain normal levels of vitamin D.

Implementing the assessment of vitamin D synthesis on an individual level in personalized medicine could be a significant step in improving modern and accurate medical services [15]. However, before introducing this into practice, it is necessary to study population-specific factors affecting vitamin D synthesis.

The findings in this article will help in identifying the risk of diseases associated with vitamin D and in implementing preventive measures. When vitamin D levels are low or its metabolism is disrupted due to genetic factors, there may be an increased susceptibility to diseases associated with vitamin D. Early detection of diseases, identifying at risk groups, and developing effective preventive measures to address vitamin D related issues are possible. The research results provide guidance on improving vitamin D synthesis, increasing its levels through diet and supplements, and properly regulating sun exposure to help prevent diseases.

Research Objective: The aim of this study is to evaluate the variability of vitamin D based on sunlight exposure quantity and quality, skin pigmentation, body weight and fat content, diet, physical activity, season and climate, clothing, skin care, and health status among four groups: 652 elite athletes, 100 patients diagnosed with reproductive system diseases (infertility) who have started treatment, 100 individuals diagnosed with bone disorders who have started treatment, and 100 conditionally healthy individuals. Additionally, the study aims to identify specific characteristics of vitamin D for each individual organism by examining polymorphisms in the vitamin D receptor (VDR) gene.

Materials and Methods

Samples Collection and DNA Extraction: Biological samples were collected between 2020 and 2023. Blood samples were drawn from veins into 3% EDTA (ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid) vacuum tubes intended for hematological studies, and were used for both vitamin D level measurements and DNA extraction.

DNA extraction was performed using QIAamp DNA Blood Kits 250 (QIAGEN Inc., Valencia, CA, USA). The concentration of the extracted DNA was determined by comparing to a fluorescent standard using a Qubit 2.0 Fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). DNA samples were diluted to working concentrations of 20-40 ng/μl and stored frozen at -20°C. In the analysis, the genomic DNA quantity in all DNA preparations was found to be greater than 1 ng/μl, so the DNA samples were sufficiently diluted for further studies.

Genotyping and PCR Analysis: For the identification of genotype polymorphisms in the VDR FokI T>C and VDR BsmI G>A alleles, fluorescently labeled allele-specific primer sets from Limited Liability Company Scientific and Production Company "Litekh" (Moscow, Russia) were used. DNA samples were analyzed using the Dtlite4 Real-Time PCR with a 48-well automated amplifier. The PCR program included: initial denaturation at 50°C for 120 seconds and at 94°C for 120 seconds, followed by 45 cycles for 10 seconds at 94°C for denaturation, and for 20 seconds at 60°C for primer annealing and polymerase chain reaction. The melting curve analysis was performed from 27°C to 75°C at 1°C per step for 5 seconds (fluorescence measurement was conducted at each step). Allele-specific FAM and HEX detectors correspond to the 1 and 2 alleles of the gene in the DNA samples (Figure 1).

A - FAM/FAM (2/2 alleles) - Homozygous genotype

B - FAM/HEX (1/2 alleles) - Heterozygous genotype

C - HEX/HEX (1/1 alleles) - Homozygous genotype

Figure 1. Results of real-time polymerase chain reaction (Real-Time PCR) for alleles and genotypes in genes: A - FAM/FAM (2/2 alleles) - Homozygous genotype; B - FAM/HEX (1/2 alleles) - Heterozygous genotype; C - HEX/HEX (1/1 alleles) - Homozygous genotype.

The amount of vitamin D in the blood is determined using the Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) method [8]. In this method, a microtiter plate or well is coated with antibodies or antigens specific to vitamin D. Blood serum or plasma is added, and vitamin D binds to the antibodies or antigens on the microtiter plate or well. Unbound substances are washed away using a wash buffer. The enzyme-linked antibody or antigen binds with a substrate, and this reaction is colorimetric, depending on the enzyme's activity.

After the enzyme reaction, the optical density (OD) of the microtiter plate or well is measured using a spectrophotometer (tetramethylbenzidine substrate - 450 nm wavelength). The obtained optical density value is compared with standard calibrated samples to determine the concentration of vitamin D in the tested blood sample.

The most accurate time for determining the amount of vitamin D (25-hydroxyvitamin D, 25(OH)D) in the blood is during the summer and winter seasons. These seasons are suitable for

showing seasonal variations in vitamin D levels in the human body. Summer is considered the period with the highest sunlight exposure, during which vitamin D levels reaches to its peak. The highest levels of vitamin D in the blood are found in the summer, which helps to check if a person is adequately provided with optimal levels of vitamin D. In winter, sunlight exposure decreases, which can lead to lower vitamin D levels in the blood. Therefore, conducting an analysis during this time is appropriate for identifying the risk of vitamin D deficiency.

Table 1.

Absolute quantities of genotypes and their frequency of occurrence

Group(n)	VDR FokI T>C rs2228570			VDR BsmI G>A rs1544410		
	TT	TC	CC	GG	GA	AA
Athletes (652)	313(48%))	228(35%))	111(17%))	553(85%)	76(12%))	23(3%))
Patients with Reproductive System Diseases (100)	30(30%)	53(53%)	17(17%)	79(79%)	15(15%)	6(6%)
Individuals with Bone Disorder Diagnosis (100)	26(26%)	40(40%)	34(34%)	78(78%)	10(10%)	12(12%)
Conditionally Healthy Individuals (100)	52(52%)	38(38%)	10(10%)	89(89%)	9(9%)	2(2%)

Research Results and Analysis

The results for each genotype were analyzed using the χ^2 test to determine statistically significant differences between groups. The χ^2 value for VDR FokI T>C (rs2228570) was 14.1 with a p-value of 0.000000252, indicating a highly significant difference in genotype distribution between groups (p-value < 0.05). This suggests that the genotypes are not distributed equally among different groups, with some genotypes occurring more frequently in specific groups compared to others.

For VDR BsmI G>A (rs1544410), the χ^2 value was 15.5 with a p-value of 0.00493, showing a significant difference in genotype distribution as well (p-value < 0.05). However, this difference is considerably less pronounced compared to the VDR FokI T>C polymorphism.

Analysis of Results

The χ^2 and p-values for comparisons between groups showed the following results:

For athletes versus individuals with reproductive system disorders:

VDR FokI T>C (rs2228570): $\chi^2 = 13.71$, p-value: 0.00106 (significant difference)

VDR BsmI G>A (rs1544410): $\chi^2 = 2.52$, p-value: 0.283 (no significant difference)

For athletes versus individuals with bone degradation diagnoses:

VDR FokI T>C (rs2228570): $\chi^2 = 22.89$, p-value: 1.07e-05 (significant difference)

VDR BsmI G>A (rs1544410): $\chi^2 = 14.06$, p-value: 0.00088 (significant difference)

For athletes versus healthy controls:

VDR FokI T>C (rs2228570): $\chi^2 = 3.17$, p-value: 0.205 (no significant difference)

VDR BsmI G>A (rs1544410): $\chi^2 = 1.33$, p-value: 0.515 (no significant difference)

For individuals with reproductive system disorders versus individuals with bone degradation diagnoses:

VDR FokI T>C (rs2228570): $\chi^2 = 7.77$, p-value: 0.0206 (significant difference)

VDR BsmI G>A (rs1544410): $\chi^2 = 3.01$, p-value: 0.222 (no significant difference)

For individuals with reproductive system disorders versus healthy controls:

VDR FokI T>C (rs2228570): $\chi^2 = 10.19$, p-value: 0.00613 (significant difference)

VDR BsmI G>A (rs1544410): $\chi^2 = 4.10$, p-value: 0.129 (no significant difference)

For individuals with bone degradation diagnoses versus healthy controls:

VDR FokI T>C (rs2228570): $\chi^2 = 21.81$, p-value: 1.84e-05 (significant difference)

VDR BsmI G>A (rs1544410): $\chi^2 = 7.92$, p-value: 0.0191 (significant difference)

The results indicate that there are significant differences in the distribution of VDR FokI T>C (rs2228570) polymorphism among athletes, individuals with reproductive system disorders, those with bone degradation diagnoses, and healthy controls. Particularly notable differences were observed between athletes and individuals with bone degradation diagnoses, as well as between individuals with bone degradation and healthy controls. These findings suggest that the VDR FokI T>C polymorphism may be associated with specific diseases and physical conditions.

The VDR BsmI G>A (rs1544410) polymorphism also shows significant differences between some groups, but these are less pronounced. Significant differences were noted between athletes and individuals with bone degradation diagnoses, and between individuals with bone degradation and healthy controls. These results imply that the VDR BsmI G>A polymorphism might influence bone metabolism.

Overall, this study suggests that the VDR FokI T>C polymorphism is more strongly associated with various diseases and physical conditions, while the VDR BsmI G>A polymorphism has a somewhat lesser degree of association. The significant differences in genotype distribution among various groups highlight the role of these polymorphisms in specific biological processes. The findings may provide insights into how these genetic variations are linked to physical activity levels and bone health.

Based on the distribution of VDR FokI T>C (rs2228570) and VDR BsmI G>A (rs1544410) polymorphism genotypes, associations with various diseases and conditions have been identified. These genetic markers offer the potential for early diagnosis and prevention of various diseases in the future. The polymorphisms associated with VDR receptors play an important role in human health and may lead to more comprehensive research in the future to clarify their relationship with health and physical activity. This genetic information can be used to enhance strategies for physical activity, disease prevention, and treatment.

To analyze genetic diversity among different ethnic groups and populations, we need to first review results from studies conducted on various populations and compare them with our own findings. Below are the distribution data of the polymorphisms being investigated across different populations. The VDR FokI T>C (rs2228570) polymorphism varies among different global populations [20, 22]. In Europeans, the TT genotype is typically observed in about 30-40% of cases, while the TC and CC genotypes are present in approximately 50-60%. In East Asian and African populations, the CC genotype is relatively higher, around 20-30%. In our study groups, the frequency of the TT genotype (48-52%) is considerably higher compared to European populations [22]. Additionally, the CC genotype is found to be significantly more common (34%) in individuals diagnosed with bone disorders [20]. Comparisons of VDR BsmI (rs1544410) polymorphism analyses show that GA and AA genotypes are more prevalent in Europeans and Americans (20-30%). In Asian and African populations, the GG genotype is more common, but

the high frequency observed in our study groups (78-89%) is significantly higher compared to other global populations [21, 23]. This may be related to geographical or genetic factors.

The provided data reflect the distribution of VDR gene polymorphisms among different populations with specific percentage indicators. The distribution of each allele may vary depending on an individual's genetic traits and geographic region. This information is crucial in personalized medicine, particularly in the prevention and treatment of diseases. The evolutionary development of humanity has required adaptation to various geographic and climatic conditions. Naturally, this has resulted in different genetic mutations under selective pressure. The continuous variability process in genes has led to the emergence of new stable mutations in the human gene pool, and natural selection has preserved or increased their frequency.

In the study, 475 (71%) male and 195 (29%) female athletes participated. There was no significant difference in Vitamin D levels between genders, with a p-value of 0.354 (no significant difference). The prevalence of Vitamin D deficiency among athletes in open sports was 14%, while it was 39% among athletes in closed sports. The statistical evaluation between these two groups showed $\chi^2 = 15.47$ and p-value < 0.001 ($p < 0.05$), indicating a significant difference in Vitamin D deficiency prevalence among athletes in closed sports. A substantial difference in the prevalence of Vitamin D deficiency between open and closed sports was observed. Vitamin D deficiency is significantly higher among athletes in closed sports ($p < 0.001$), suggesting a higher risk of Vitamin D deficiency in these athletes. Future attention is needed for athletes who train in enclosed environments and cannot benefit from sunlight exposure. On the other hand, it is important to remember the positive impact of Vitamin D on preventing chronic diseases. A normal level of Vitamin D enhances the quality of life for athletes, similar to the general population. Genetic identification of Vitamin D deficiency in athletes can provide practical recommendations for sports federation doctors. Although evidence is limited, Vitamin D plays a role in preventing muscle injuries and stress [16]. This is particularly relevant for athletes training in enclosed spaces who cannot access sunlight. Conversely, the positive impact of Vitamin D on preventing chronic diseases should be acknowledged. A normal level of Vitamin D improves the quality of life for athletes, as it does for the general population. Vitamin D levels below 20 ng/mL (50 nmol/L) are generally considered deficient and may increase susceptibility to various diseases. However, low levels of Vitamin D do not necessarily lead to serious health problems for everyone, and some individuals may be in good health despite low levels. While low Vitamin D levels can lead to health issues, they may be sufficient for normal life in some individuals. For such individuals, other factors, including genetic characteristics, lifestyle, and Vitamin D intake, play an important role. Therefore, personal Vitamin D levels should be assessed considering not only general guidelines but also individual physiology.

To assess seasonal variations in Vitamin D levels, the study included 216 athletes and 100 healthy individuals as a control group. A difference of 8-15 ng/mL between the low levels in winter and the high levels in summer was observed. In Uzbekistan, seasonal changes and lifestyle suggest that Vitamin D levels are higher in summer and lower in winter. Evaluating the population's Vitamin D levels and taking additional measures when necessary (such as Vitamin D supplements) is important. In Central Asia, summer days are long and sunny, providing favorable conditions for Vitamin D synthesis in the skin. Additionally, the abundance of fruits, vegetables, and other food sources in summer provides more opportunities for Vitamin D intake through diet. Therefore, Vitamin D levels in the blood may be higher during summer months. Furthermore, higher

temperatures in summer encourage people to spend more time outdoors, increasing exposure to sunlight. In winter, however, days are shorter and sunlight intensity is lower. This reduces Vitamin D synthesis in the skin, resulting in lower Vitamin D levels. Cold temperatures in winter may lead people to spend more time indoors or in enclosed buildings, contributing to decreased Vitamin D levels. In Uzbekistan, limited food varieties in winter and reduced Vitamin D intake through diet may occur. Additionally, cultural or religious practices among Uzbeks, such as spending more time indoors or covering body parts (e.g., the traditional practice of covering women), might limit exposure to sunlight to some extent. In such cases, low Vitamin D levels may be expected regardless of the season.

Human bodies contain Vitamin D in two forms: D₂ (ergocalciferol) and D₃ (cholecalciferol) [19].

Vitamin D₂, or ergocalciferol, is one of the two main forms of Vitamin D. It is found in significant amounts in plant and fungal sources and is an important nutrient for the human body [18]. Vitamin D₂ is absorbed into the blood through the intestinal microvilli without energy expenditure. Once in the bloodstream, ergocalciferol (D₂) is converted to 25-hydroxyvitamin D₂ (25(OH)₂D₂) by the enzyme 25-hydroxylase in the liver. This metabolite is the primary circulating form of Vitamin D and is measured in laboratory tests to assess overall Vitamin D status and deficiency. Subsequently, 25(OH)₂D₂ travels to the kidneys where it is converted to the active form of Vitamin D, 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D₂ (1,25(OH)₂D₂), by the enzyme 1- α -hydroxylase. This active form, known as calcitriol, plays a crucial role in calcium and phosphorus metabolism, immune system function, and other physiological processes [17]. The active form of Vitamin D, 25(OH)₂D₂, can generally be stored in the body for several weeks to several months. However, the efficacy and retention time of Vitamin D₂ are typically lower compared to Vitamin D₃ [19].

Vitamin D₃ (cholecalciferol) is produced in the skin under the influence of ultraviolet B (UVB) rays. Additionally, it can be obtained from dietary sources, such as fish oils and foods fortified with synthetic Vitamin D₃ [16]. UVB rays convert 7-dehydrocholesterol in the skin into Vitamin D₃, which is then transferred to the blood. In the bloodstream, Vitamin D₃ binds to vitamin D-binding protein (DBP) and is transported to the liver. In the liver, Vitamin D₃ is converted to 25-hydroxyvitamin D₃ (25(OH)₂D₃, calcidiol) by the enzyme 25-hydroxylase. This substance circulates in the blood and is commonly used to assess overall Vitamin D levels. In the kidneys, 25(OH)₂D₃ is further converted to 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D₃ (1,25(OH)₂D₃, calcitriol) by the enzyme 1 α -hydroxylase (CYP27B1) [17]. This active form of Vitamin D₃ is crucial for carrying out various physiological functions. 1,25(OH)₂D₃ increases calcium and phosphorus absorption in the intestines and helps mobilize calcium from the bones. The level of 25(OH)₂D₃ in the blood indicates the status of overall Vitamin D and can remain active for up to 2-3 months [18].

The article "Serum 1,25-Dihydroxyvitamin D: What's Normal?" analyzes 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D levels and their normal ranges based on data from healthy populations in the USA, Germany, France, Britain, Italy, and Switzerland. The conclusion of the article indicates that the 1,25(OH)₂D₃ form is predominant in human blood. According to the research findings, the D₃ form is more prevalent in the blood compared to the D₂ form, constituting 85-90% of the total vitamin D concentration. LC-MS/MS (liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry) method was used in the analysis of vitamin D [8].

The article "Serum 1,25-Dihydroxyvitamin D Levels in Latin American Populations" is based on data from healthy individuals in Brazil and Mexico. The conclusion of this article shows that the $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$ form constitutes 90-95% of the concentration in human blood [5].

The article "Serum 1,25-Dihydroxyvitamin D_3 and 1,25-Dihydroxyvitamin D_2 Levels in Asian Populations" stands out due to its findings that 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D levels are significantly lower than normal in populations from Turkey, China, India, and South Korea. The research indicates that the D_3 form is more common in the blood compared to the D_2 form. In India: low $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$ levels were found to be around 50%. The average vitamin D level was found to be in the range of 25.1-30.5 nmol/L. In China: low levels were around 30%, often in the range of 20-35 nmol/L. In South Korea: most of the population had levels as low as 25 nmol/L [1].

The article "Vitamin D Status and 1,25-Dihydroxyvitamin D Levels in African Populations" aims to evaluate overall vitamin D levels in various African populations, investigate their health impacts, and identify vitamin D deficiencies. Data from healthy individuals in African countries such as Nigeria, Kenya, Egypt, and Sudan revealed that low levels can lead to disturbances in calcium and phosphorus metabolism, skeletal disorders, and osteomalacia. In Nigeria, Kenya, and Egypt, $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$ levels were found to be around 20-30 pmol/L (0.020 - 0.030 ng/mL) [2].

Seasonal variations observed in the range of 8-15 ng/mL may be related to differences in concentrations of $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_2$ and $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$. Research indicates that $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$ is the primary biologically active form of vitamin D in the blood and is a key factor in maintaining overall vitamin D levels. The levels of $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$ generally fluctuate less compared to 25-hydroxyvitamin D ($25(\text{OH})\text{D}$), as its levels are tightly regulated by homeostatic processes. However, $25(\text{OH})\text{D}$ levels are more affected by seasonal changes and reflect the overall vitamin D stores. During seasonal variations, differences between the concentrations of $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_2$ and $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$ are significant. Typically, the level of $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$ is less affected by seasonal changes, as this form is strictly regulated by physiological processes. On the other hand, $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_2$ levels are more closely related to seasonal variations and indicate the overall vitamin D reserves. Therefore, $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$ accurately reflects the overall vitamin D status in our region and its levels may vary significantly with seasonal changes. Based on these studies, it is shown that while $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$ levels may remain stable during seasonal variations, $25(\text{OH})\text{D}$ levels can fluctuate considerably.

Moreover, the analysis of results indicates that vitamin D synthesis occurs in the skin under the influence of ultraviolet (UVB) rays. The melanin pigment in the skin can absorb UV rays and reduce vitamin D synthesis. As a result, individuals with darker skin tones tend to synthesize less vitamin D, as seen in African populations where the skin contains more melanin. The research findings also highlight differences in 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D levels and their concentrations across various populations, confirming the impact of skin color and geographic location. For example, in Latin American and European countries, where sunlight exposure varies and the melanin content in the skin of the population is lower, $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$ levels are found to be higher.

In the studies, patients who started treatment for reproductive system disorders (infertility) and those who began treatment for bone deterioration mostly showed vitamin D ($25(\text{OH})\text{D}$) levels in the blood ranging from 6–16 ng/mL, indicating deficiency and values at critical thresholds that are hazardous to health. Notably, in women starting treatment for reproductive system disorders, the levels of vitamin D that were considered hazardous to health

were found to be exceedingly high. In this context, a key factor distinguishing these cases was the presence of conditions such as infertility or miscarriage in women. Most individuals starting treatment for bone deterioration were those who had been diagnosed with bone deterioration following the COVID-19 pandemic. The observed vitamin D deficiency in this group may be related to a weakened immune system and the prolonged effects of the virus on the body. Vitamin D plays a crucial role in bone health and is also significant in supporting the immune system.

Vitamin D receptors (VDR) modulate the effects of vitamin D in the body, and these receptors have genetic polymorphisms that vary across different populations [16]. For example, VDR FokI and VDR BsmI polymorphisms can lead to variations in the effects of vitamin D across different ethnic groups. These genetic factors, together with the complications following COVID-19 infection, may contribute to the likelihood of bone deterioration and vitamin D deficiency [16].

The results of this study provide information on how VDR FokI T>C (rs2228570) and VDR BsmI G>A (rs1544410) polymorphisms affect differences between athletes, individuals with reproductive system disorders, individuals undergoing treatment for bone deterioration, and healthy controls. Based on these results, it is recommended to conduct further research on vitamin D polymorphisms and their health impacts in various ethnic groups, and to monitor vitamin D levels taking into account individual physiological characteristics.

Conclusions:

The VDR FokI T>C (rs2228570) polymorphism exhibits significant and substantial differences across various groups. As indicated, there are notable variations in the indicators of this polymorphism between athletes and individuals undergoing treatment for bone deterioration. Significant differences are also observed between individuals with reproductive system disorders and healthy controls. The VDR FokI T>C (rs2228570) polymorphism is associated with bone metabolism and reproductive health.

The VDR BsmI G>A (rs1544410) polymorphism also shows differences among various groups, but these differences are less pronounced compared to VDR FokI T>C. Significant variations are observed among athletes and individuals undergoing treatment for bone deterioration, but differences with healthy controls are less significant.

VDR polymorphisms have been shown to vary among different populations and genotypes. This presents an opportunity to utilize genetic markers for early diagnosis and prevention of diseases.

Seasonal variations in Vitamin D levels are explained by the differences between summer and winter levels. Vitamin D levels are higher in summer and lower in winter, primarily related to sun exposure and dietary patterns.

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